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Multi-Label Text Classification with Transfer Learning for Policy Documents

The Case of the Sustainable Development Goals

Samuel Rodríguez Medina

Uppsala University
Department of Linguistics and Philology
Master's Programme in Language Technology
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Supervisors:

Mats Dahllöf, Uppsala University, Sweden

Aidin Niamir, Senckenberg Biodiversity and Climate Research Institute,
Frankfurt am Main, Germany

Maral Dadvar, WISS Research Group at Stuttgart Media University, Stuttgart,
Germany

Abstract

We created and analyzed a text classification dataset from freely-available web documents from the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals. We then used it to train and compare different multi-label text classifiers with the aim of exploring the alternatives for methods that facilitate the search of information of this type of documents.

We explored the effectiveness of deep learning and transfer learning in text classification by fine-tuning different pre-trained language representations — Word2Vec, GloVe, ELMo, ULMFiT and BERT. We also compared these approaches against a baseline of more traditional algorithms without using transfer learning. More specifically, we used multinomial Naive Bayes, logistic regression, k-nearest neighbors and Support Vector Machines.

We then analyzed the results of our experiments quantitatively and qualitatively. The best results in terms of micro-averaged F1 scores and AUROC are obtained by BERT. However, it is also interesting that the second best classifier in terms of micro-averaged F1 scores is the Support Vector Machines, closely followed by the logistic regression classifier, which both have the advantage of being less computationally expensive than BERT. The results also show a close relation between our dataset size and the effectiveness of the classifiers.

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1 Introduction

In 2015 all member states of the United Nations (UN) adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a set of 17 objectives which are part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN General Assembly, 2015) and include goals such as taking immediate action to combat climate change, end poverty, achieve gender equality, and end hunger. They serve as the development road map for member governments to know what direction their policies regarding these areas should take for the next decade.

The scientific community, policy makers, politicians, private sector agents, and any other actors involved in the SDGs to any extent need an efficient system to support them retrieve the relevant documents and information which will help them research, advance and monitor the goals.

However, the overwhelming amount of information related to the SDGs and its multidisciplinary nature make it time-consuming for these users to find the relevant information. For example, a document that is about coffee production in Colombia and its exportation to other countries is directly related to SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) but it also contains information on SDG 13 (Climate Action), SDG 15 (Life on Land) and SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation). Without an automatized way of finding these labels, users need to spend considerable amounts of their time to find that information. In order to address that problem, we have explored different multi-label text classification methods for SDGs-related texts.

At the moment of writing this thesis and to the best of our knowledge, such SDGs-dedicated and automatized system does not exist.

1.1 Purpose

In this section we look at the two purposes of this master thesis.

1.1.1 Multi-label text classifier

Our main purpose is to study and implement multi-label text classifiers of SDGs documents. These classifiers take a text as input and automatically detect the SDGs labels. In the example from the introduction about coffee production, our classifier should be able to label such document with labels 6, 12, 13 and 15.

To find the most effective classifier we explored multiple methods. We looked into transfer learning, fine-tuned different pre-trained models and compared them against a baseline of more traditional machine learning algorithms.

1.1.2 Dataset

Our second purpose is to create a multi-label classification dataset with texts from the SDGs with which we will carry out the different multi-label text classification experiments.

In order to create the dataset we first gathered a collection of documents crawled from SDGs-related websites. These documents explicitly mention goals in the content paragraphs or in the filenames so we created a set of regular expressions rules to automatically extract those texts and their labels when they are unambiguously referring to the SDGs.

1.2 Overview and challenges

In this section we give an overview of the challenges that we identified in the preliminary analysis of our project.

1.2.1 Implicit information

The implicit information in SDGs documents lies at the center of the problem we are trying to solve. In many documents, the SDGs are not explicitly mentioned or used in the metadata. For instance, if a research paper is about aerodynamics of aircrafts, that document might implicitly contain information related to climate change, since a better aerodynamic might increase the aircrafts' efficiency in terms of fuel consumption, which subsequently imply a smaller CO2 footprint. However, the expression climate change might not appear in such document.

1.2.2 Scope

Another important challenge is the scope of the SDGs. Each one of the SDGs are a separate field of study for which entire information retrieval systems are built. For example, health alone comprises multiple dedicated systems and databases, such as Medline or PubMed, and whole areas of study like health informatics with extensive academic literature.

Additionally, each of these goals has a set of 169 specific targets and 232 indicators to measure the progress achieved in each of those targets. To illustrate how deep the scope gets, one of the thirteen targets of SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being) is *By 2030, end the epidemics of AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria and neglected tropical diseases and combat hepatitis, water-borne diseases and other communicable diseases*. AIDS, tuberculosis and malaria alone are vast areas of study with extensive literature.

Furthermore, these are also areas of study which are constantly growing. For example, in a bibliometric study by Haunschild et al. (2016) it stated that the number of climate change papers between 1980 and 2014 had doubled every 5-6 years.

1.2.3 Interdependency

As it is pointed out in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development itself, the SDGs are a integrated set of priorities and objectives that are interdependent

and interrelated. This interdependency happens often in a implicit way as it was previously pointed out and adds another layer of complexity to our project as it hinders the identification of the SDGs.

1.2.4 Labelled data

Whereas there is no available labelled dataset for text classification of the SDGs (see Section 2.1), there exists nevertheless a considerable amount of online textual data from which we can automatically extract labels by searching for patterns in them. However, the different formats of the documents are quite challenging to work with. In Section 3.1, we explain how we used this textual data in order to create our dataset.

2 Background

In this section we explore previous work related to this thesis.

2.1 SDGs-related projects

When doing our background research, we found multiple information retrieval projects related to the SDGs.

One of them was the Sustainable Development Interface Ontology (SDGIO) (UNEP, 2016), an ontology created by the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) in collaboration with several ontology specialists.

The UN has also a platform called Unite Ideas (UN, n.d.) which puts forward different challenges to advance the SDGs, human rights, peace and security, etc. The challenges, which are open to anyone to participate in them, include information extraction for the UN General Assembly resolutions, finding insights on the status of the SDGs, and many others. One of the proposed challenges was SciTechMatcher, which consisted of building a search and recommendation engine for science, technology and innovation. From that challenge, there was a follow-up project by the UN interagency task team on Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) for the SDGs. Their aim was to create an online platform which would help users find information about science, technology and innovation initiatives related to the SDGs.

Finally, Zindi, which defines itself as *a community of data scientists solving Africa's toughest challenges*, organized a text classification challenge focused on SDG 3 (Zindi, 2018). In their challenge the objective was to classify the texts with the 27 indicators of SDG 3, instead of all the SDGs.

2.2 Text classification

Text classification is the area of study of information retrieval concerned with the classification of text samples into predefined classes. Depending on how many of these classes or labels are assigned to each sample, there are three main types of text classification — binary, multi-class and multi-label.

Binary text classifiers assign one of two possible labels to each sample. This is the common approach, for instance, for sentiment analysis. A popular example in the field is the **IMDB** dataset of users movie reviews created by Maas et al. (2011) whose reviews belong to two pre-defined classes indicating whether the movie review is positive or negative.

Multi-class text classifiers assign to each sample one label from a set of more than two classes. An illustrative example is the **BBC dataset** (Greene and Cunningham, 2006), which consists of 2225 texts labelled with one of the following classes — business, entertainment, politics, sport and tech.

Lastly, in multi-label text classification the model assigns one or more labels from a set of more than one class to each sample.

There are multiple approaches to multi-label text classification (Manning et al., 2009). The samples can be manually classified by domain-experts, for example. This method can nonetheless be costly and time-consuming. It also has the disadvantage that for certain fields it might be difficult to find those domain-experts in charge of classifying the samples.

Another approach is rule-based systems. Here a domain-expert creates rules through regular expressions or boolean standing queries to find keywords that belong to a certain class. Although this method can be quite effective, it lacks scalability when the content is too complex or is constantly growing. Anything not considered in those rules is left out of the retrieval. And as mentioned before, it might also be complicated to find such experts at times, which in turn can make these systems expensive to develop.

The last approach is machine learning. Since in machine learning the models are trainable, their main advantage is that they can be applied to unseen cases without explicitly defining the unseen events.

In the following section we introduce some commonly used machine learning methods employed in multi-label text classification. Even though machine learning and deep learning are part the same field of study (being the latter a sub-field of the former), in this thesis we separate them into two groups simply because it is convenient and it makes it easier to compare them.

2.3 Machine Learning in text classification

Herrera et al. (2016) give an extensive overview on multi-label classification which, even though it is not only focused on text, cover the most basic and relevant aspects that the field presented up until 2016. The authors categorize the most common approaches to the multi-label classification problem into three: data transformation, method adaptation and ensembles approaches.

Data transformation consist in transforming the multi-label problem into one of more simpler ones. The most common approach of data transformation is binary relevance. With this method, a classifier is trained on each class and needs to learn whether a label is relevant or not for a given sample.

The second approach, method adaptation, consists of adapting binary classification algorithms so that they can deal with multiple labels.

And the last approach, ensemble, consists of combining several classifiers with the assumption that they will be able to capture different bias which combined will achieve better results than if they are applied individually. This method therefore does not tackle the multi-label problem directly, but deal with related problems such as class imbalance, i.e. having considerably more samples for some classes than others.

In terms of algorithms, Baeza-Yates and Ribeiro-Neto (2008) list the most representative supervised classification methods in decision trees, nearest neighbors, relevance feedback, Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machines and ensemble.

As stated in Herrera et al. (2016), most of these algorithms can be used as classifiers for multi-label problems by the transformation-based OVA (One Vs All)

approach, also known as OVR (One Vs Rest). With this approach one classifier is trained per class so that when classifying an unseen sample it needs to decide whether that class is relevant or not for that sample.

Formally, the multi-label text classification problem in machine learning can be expressed, as explained by Baeza-Yates and Ribeiro-Neto (2008), as follows. We have a collection of samples S , each represented in a vector space of features, and a set of classes $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{17}\}$, where a text classifier is a binary function $F : C \times S \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ that assigns a 0 or 1 to each pair $[s_j, c_p]$, where s_j is a sample $\in S$ and c_p a label from the set of classes $\in C$.

An important step of the problem formulated above is feature selection. Since the texts that we need to classify can be quite long, we need a way to choose only those features or terms that can best represent each sample into a vector space of features in order to make it easier for the algorithms to classify each text sample into the different classes.

One of the most common approaches to feature selection is TF-IDF. The first part of this method, Term Frequency (TF), represents how often a given term t occurs in one sample or document. The second, Inverse Document Frequency (IDF), represents the total number of samples or documents N over the number of samples or documents in which that given term t occurs, calculated with the log to base 10 as seen in Equation 2.1 below.

$$IDF_t = \log \frac{N}{DF_t} \quad (2.1)$$

Finally, TF-IDF weights of each term are given by multiplying the TF and IDF of each term in our sample collection, and it gives higher weights to those terms occurring frequently in fewer samples and lower weights to terms occurring frequently over all the documents.

Many of the aforementioned machine learning algorithms have been applied to text classification tasks with considerable effectiveness in the past. Some examples are Ren et al. (2014) and Ahmed et al. (2015). In the next sections we will give an overview of some of the most common algorithms.

2.3.1 Multinomial Naive Bayes

In its most basic form, Naive Bayes text classifiers, as explained by Baeza-Yates and Ribeiro-Neto (2008), assign to each sample-class the probability that a sample, represented by a vector of binary weights, belong to that class by applying the Bayes theorem. The binary weights indicate whether a term appears in the sample or not, and once all the probabilities are calculated the classifier assigns the class with the highest probabilities to the corresponding sample.

However, this form of Naive Bayes does not take into account the frequency of the terms. This is something that is considered by the multinomial Naive Bayes, which is generally more effective (Mccallum and Nigam, 2001) for text classification.

2.3.2 K-nearest neighbors

The k-nearest neighbors classifier (k-NN) is an on-demand classifier (Baeza-Yates and Ribeiro-Neto, 2008), which means that it does not compute the classification probabilities beforehand but every time a new sample is provided. The classifier looks at the sample's closest neighbors in a predefined metrics space with a distance function and assigns the class of the neighbors to the new sample.

2.3.3 Support Vector Machines

Support Vector Machines (SVM) is a kernel method proposed by Cortes and Vapnik (1995) and have proven to be considerably effective in text classification (Joachims, 1999). As explained by Baeza-Yates and Ribeiro-Neto (2008), the idea behind the most basic SVM is a binary classifier in a high-dimensional vector space where samples are represented as points and whose objective is to find the decision hyperplane that divides them in one of two classes.

To calculate this hyperplane in a linear separable dataset, the classifier first locates the support vectors, which are the samples delimiting the boundaries of the classes. The lines or planes that cross the support vectors are called delimiting hyperplanes and it is between them that the classifier needs to find the decision hyperplane. Finally the decision hyperplane is selected to be the line or plane in the space that maximises the distance to the delimiting hyperplanes.

Once the decision hyperplane is learned, the classifier examines a new sample and assigns it a label depending on which position of the decision hyperplane it is located.

2.3.4 Logistic regression

The last algorithm we examine from the group of machine learning, logistic regression, is closely related to deep learning's neural networks as the latter can be seen, in a very simplified manner, as multiple stacked logistic regression classifiers (Jurafsky and H. Martin, 2019).

The most basic logistic regression algorithm is a binary classifier that first multiplies the features of each sample by its weights and add a bias, and later applies a sigmoid function to obtain a probability of the sample belonging to one class or the other. The difference between this probability and the actual value of the class we want to predict is calculated with the cross-entropy loss function, which is then minimized with gradient descent.

Contrary to Naive Bayes, logistic regression does not assume the independence of each of the sample's features, which means that when data is available in considerable size logistic regression tends to be more effective (Ng and Jordan, 2002), although Naive Bayes generally works well with limited data and it is faster to execute.

2.4 Deep learning

Deep learning can be defined as a subfield of machine learning (Chollet, 2017) which learns representation from data through the use of successive layers of

increasing representation stacked in neural networks that are learnt simultaneously. The main advantage of these models over the machine learning methods that we explained in the previous section is not only that they are more effective when a lot of data is available but that they also completely automate the feature selection. So whereas in the previous machine learning methods it was crucial to manually find a good representation of the input data so that the methods could apply simple transformations, neural networks learn the representation layers automatically and jointly, which means that if a weight changes in a certain layer, all the related weights will also be modified automatically as necessary.

On the other hand though, the disadvantage of neural networks is that they often require much more computational power (like the use of GPUs) than the machine learning methods previously discussed.

Neural networks started having an important impact by the end of the first decade of 2000, especially in computer vision. In the last five years they have also had a considerable impact in text classification, more specifically in Large-scale Multi-Label Text Classification (LMTC) and Extreme Multi-Label Text Classification (XMC). LMTC, mostly represented by the [LSHTC challenges](#) (Nam et al., 2013) from 2009 to 2014, were based on datasets which contained hundred of thousands of classes. XMC, on the other hand, presents a challenge of labelling every instance in a corpus with a subset of labels from a set of up to millions of classes. Papers like You et al. (2018) or J. Liu et al. (2017) use diverse neural nets implementations for this challenge.

Another area of study that has had an important impact in Natural Language Processing (NLP) has been transfer learning, with the proposition of different types of word embeddings and pre-trained language models.

In the next sections we will go over some of the most common neural network models, and then we will explain transfer learning and how it can be relevant to text classification.

2.4.1 CNNs

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) create a matrix of word embeddings for each sentence to which convolutional filters called kernels are applied with all possible windows of words in order to extract different features. After that, a max-pooling strategy is applied in order to reduce the layers' output dimensionality and to keep them in a fixed size (Young et al., 2017). Deep convolutional networks are created by stacking combinations of these convolutional layers.

As mentioned by Chollet (2017), CNNs are competitive with RNNs and can be a much faster alternative to RNNs for tasks like text classification. Therefore multiple studies have used CNNs for multi-label text classification. Peng et al. (2019), for example, proposed an attention graph capsule recurrent CNN for large scale text classification on three different classification sets. Parwez et al. (2019), on the other hand, proposed CNNs with generic and domain-specific word embeddings for multi-label text classification with microblogging data and obtained improved accuracy compared to machine learning approaches.

2.4.2 RNNs and LSTM

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) process one by one the elements of a sequence and recurrently apply certain tasks to each element, whose computation is dependent on the previous computations, which means the model keeps memory of the previous elements with respect to the target. This memory is crucial for RNNs since the semantic meaning of sequences often relies on previous elements.

Another important aspect of RNNs is their availability to handle inputs of variable length, which is something that CNNs cannot do and can have an impact on text classification tasks.

However, RNNs have the *vanishing gradient problem*, which means that in practice when a RNN is run many times the gradient becomes so small that the weights of the first layers do not update anymore, so the model forgets information that is far away from the current feature. To solve that Long Short-Term Memory was proposed by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997).

2.5 Transfer Learning

Inductive transfer learning is a research problem of machine learning that deals with how knowledge can be stored, reused and transferred from previously trained models. Whereas transfer learning has been extensively used in computer vision with important success, it has not been until recent years that the NLP community has managed to successfully apply transfer learning to text (Howard et al., 2018).

For NLP, transfer learning refers more specifically to pre-trained language representations — general models that are trained on large corpora and contain a considerable amount of world-knowledge. It has proven to be very effective to train models for specific downstream tasks on top of these pre-trained language representations. This effectiveness seems to be caused by that general knowledge provided by the pre-trained models which otherwise cannot be inferred in many cases from the training set of the task at hand.

As presented by Devlin et al. (2018), in NLP there are two main types of pre-trained language representations — feature-based and fine-tuning models. Whereas the first are often used to initialize the first layer of our neural network, the latter are fine-tuned as a whole model for a specific downstream task.

In the next sections, we will give an overview on pre-trained language representations.

2.5.1 Word embeddings

An example of feature-based pre-trained language representations are word embeddings, word representations in vectors that have been learned from their context, following the hypothesis that similar words have similar contexts.

Three of the most emblematic word embeddings architectures are Word2vec, GloVe and ELMo, which we will explain over the next sections.

Word2vec

Even though there had been previous approaches to word embeddings (Collobert and Weston, 2008), it was Word2vec (Mikolov et al., 2013) that mostly popularized them. Word2vec is based on the distributional hypothesis, which refers to the fact that the meaning of the words can be inferred by its context. Word2vec can be trained with two model architectures in order to obtain the word representations — Continuous Bag-of-Words (CBOW) and Skip-gram model. The first one learns to predict a word given a window of k words around it, where the order is not taken into account.

The second architecture learns to predict words before and after a certain target word using a log-linear classifier with continuous projection layer. Words that are further from the target word are given less weight since they are usually less related to the target word.

GloVe

Global Vectors for Word Representation (GloVe) was proposed by Pennington et al. (2014) as a log-bilinear regression model that uses the occurrence counts of the words in the entire corpus when training, instead of only using a shallow window-based method such as that of Word2vec.

ELMo

Some of the limitations of Word2vec, as explained in Young et al. (2017), are that word embeddings cannot represent a combination of two or more words like idioms. They are also limited by the window size of their training, and have problems representing polysemic words.

To deal with these issues, Peters et al. (2018) introduced Embeddings from Language Models (ELMo), deep contextualized word representations that model both how words are used (syntax and semantics) and contextual variances (like polysemy). The representations are learned from the internal states of a deep bidirectional language model (biLM) trained with a LSTM on a large corpus of 30 million sentences (Chelba et al., 2013) and instead of returning a representation per word, they return a representation per contextual word. For example, the word *bank* have different senses in the three sentences below. For each one of them, ELMo would create a different embedding.

(...) areas prone to flooding, landslides, and river bank collapse (...)

(...) women have opened their own bank accounts (...)

(...) administer a child grain bank to store complementary food (...)

Regarding the use of word embeddings in multi-label text classification, an interesting study was done by Chalkidis et al. (2019), where they use Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Units (BIGRUs) with label-wise attention, and compared Word2vec and ELMo embeddings for multi-label text classification of EU legal documents, which further improved their results. Additionally, they also fine-tuned BERT (see Section 2.5.2) only with the title and recitals of every document due to the model's string length restriction, and obtain the best results in all tests except for zero-shot learning labels.

Another related work was Kant et al. (2018), where the authors use ELMo embeddings as a baseline to compare against a language model fine-tuning with a Transformer.

2.5.2 Fine-tuning language models

From 2018 to 2019 there has been a proliferation of multiple fine-tuning pre-trained language models, such as GPT (Radford et al., 2018), GPT-2 (Radford et al., 2019), Transformer-XL (Dai et al., 2019), XLNet (Yang et al., 2019) and XLM (Lample and Conneau, 2019). In the next sections we will introduce two of the earliest approaches — ULMFiT and BERT.

ULMFiT

The Universal Language Model Fine-tuning (ULMFiT), proposed by Howard and Ruder (2018), is an inductive transfer learning method which consists of three stages — 1) train a language model on a general domain corpus, 2) then fine-tune that model on a more specific corpus related to the downstream task, 3) and finally train a classifier on top of that model.

The authors also proposed *discriminative fine-tuning, slanted triangular learning rates, and gradual unfreezing*, which are explained in Section 3.3.4.

On IMDB (Maas et al., 2011) ULMFiT matched the effectiveness of training with 100 labelled texts that of *training from scratch with 10× and—given 50k unlabeled examples—with 100× more data*.

As mentioned in the paper, this approach is very useful for tasks with little labelled data and some unlabelled data.

BERT

Another important pre-trained representation model, based on the Transformer architecture introduced by Vaswani et al. (2017), is Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) by Devlin et al. (2018).

The authors argue that the main limitation of pre-training models is the unidirectionality, which means the representations are only learnt from left to right, therefore missing cataphoric references which are important for certain tasks like question answering. They propose the Masked Language Model (MLM) with a deep bidirectional Transformer, which randomly masks parts of the unlabelled input so that the model learns how to predict the masked elements from both directions. Additionally, the model also learns how to predict the next sentence with Next Sentence Prediction (NSP).

Unlike ULMFiT, BERT has only two steps — pre-training and fine-tuning. The BERT models shared by the authors were pre-trained on the BooksCorpus (800 million words) (Zhu et al., 2015) and the English Wikipedia (2500 million words). By only fine-tuning one of these pre-trained models with an additional output layer, practitioners can achieve state of the art results in downstream tasks.

Multiple successful examples of using BERT have been proposed for text classification. Chang et al. (2019), for example, propose X-BERT, a system which fine-tunes BERT by assembling different models trained on heterogeneous label

clusters. They achieve a precision @1 of 67.80% in a Extreme Multi-label Text Classification (XMTC) Wiki dataset of half a million labels.

Another study was done by Lee and Hsiang (2019), who fine-tuned BERT and achieved the state of the art in patent classification, whose best results had been previously achieved by a CNN with word embeddings.

Finally, Adhikari et al. (2019) fine-tuned BERT for document classification and achieved state of the art results in popular multi-label datasets like Reuters-21578 and arXiv Academic Paper dataset (AAPD).

2.6 Evaluation metrics

Multi-label text classifiers return predictions per sample in the form of a set of one or more labels that are evaluated against the ground truth set of labels. They might predict all, a larger or smaller proportion, or none of the labels, which means that we need to use metrics that capture these different degrees of effectiveness of our classifier.

2.6.1 Macro and Micro F1 measure

In text classification it is common to use precision, recall and F measure metrics. To understand them we can first draw a contingency table, see Table 2.1 (Manning et al., 2009).

	Relevant	Non-relevant
Retrieved	True Positives (TP)	False Positives (FP)
Not retrieved	False Negatives (FN)	True Negatives (TN)

Table 2.1: Contingency table

We then can formulate precision and recall as seen in Equations 2.2 and 2.3.

$$Prec = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2.2)$$

$$Rec = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2.3)$$

In our context and having a sample as reference, precision is defined as how many of the predicted labels actually belong to that sample, while recall is defined as to how many relevant labels from that sample were found. A metric that compromises between these two is F measure, which is formally defined as the weighted harmonic mean of precision and recall, as seen in Equation 2.4.

$$FMeasure = \frac{(\beta^2 + 1)Prec \times Rec}{\beta^2 Prec + Rec} \quad \text{where} \quad \beta^2 = \frac{1 - \alpha}{\alpha} \quad (2.4)$$

With $\alpha = 0.5$ or $\beta = 1$ both precision and recall have the same weight, which correspond to the most commonly used parameters for F measure, called F1 measure.

In multi-label classification, this is nevertheless more complicated since these metrics can be calculated at the sample or at the class level. For that reason

two averaging methods are usually proposed in the literature — macro- and micro-averaging.

Micro-averaged scores are calculated per sample instance j whereas macro-averaged scores are calculated by class m and averaged over all the classes k , as seen in the equations below.

$$Prec_{mic} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^i TP_j}{\sum_{j=1}^i TP_j + \sum_{j=1}^i FP_j} \quad (2.5) \quad Prec_{mac} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^k Prec_m}{k} \quad (2.6)$$

$$Rec_{mic} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^i TP_j}{\sum_{j=1}^i TP_j + \sum_{j=1}^i FN_j} \quad (2.7) \quad Rec_{mac} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^k Rec_m}{k} \quad (2.8)$$

The micro- and macro-averaged F measure scores are then calculated by plugging these micro and macro scores into the F measure formula shown in Equation 2.4.

The main difference between these metrics is that macro-averaged F1 treats all labels equally whereas micro-averaged F1 gives the same weight at decisions that the classifier takes in each document. In a unbalanced dataset, larger classes have a bigger impact (Manning et al., 2009), which is not considered in macro-averaged F1 measure.

Because our dataset is unbalanced in terms of samples per class (see Section 3.2), we decided to use micro-averaged F1 scores when presenting our results in Section 4.1.

2.6.2 Hamming loss

The Hamming loss is an example-based metric common in multi-label classification which, as illustrated by Equation 2.9 calculates the symmetric difference (Δ) between the set of predicted labels h and the set of true labels y for every label l and sample d , counts ($||$) all elements in this difference (which represent the wrong predictions) and normalizes them over the number of labels and samples.

$$HammingLoss = \frac{1}{dl} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^l |h_{ij} \Delta y_{ij}| \quad (2.9)$$

2.6.3 Micro AUROC

Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUROC) is a metric composed of two parts. First, Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) is based on plotting the TPs on the y axis of a graph and the FPs on its x axis (Fawcett, 2006), which creates a curve on the plot and tell us how effective our classifier is. The more data points on the northwest side of the plot, the more effective the classifier is. Once the ROC is plotted, the Area Under the Curve AUC is calculated, which is a number between 0 and 1. Random guessing usually produces an AUROC of 0.5, so our classifier should always have at least more than that.

Similarly to the micro and macro averaging scores of Section 2.6.1, we can either obtain AUC by scoring all labels or samples. In this case we decided to use

the micro-averaged score, which means that the ROC is calculated for every text sample.

2.6.4 Cross-validation

When carrying out our classification experiments we need to split the dataset in training, validation and test sets. Especially with a small datasets like ours, the obtained results might not be representative of the model as a whole and could only be dependent on those specific splits, however randomized and shuffled the selection of the samples is.

In order to tackle this problem and to guarantee the consistent stability and statistical validity of our model (Baeza-Yates and Ribeiro-Neto, 2008) we used cross-validation.

Cross-validation consists of creating k classifiers and dividing our dataset in k folds, each of which are subsequently split differently in training, validation and test subsets. Then the classifiers are trained using the training folds, and the hyperparameters are found by experimenting with different settings and validating the results against our validation folds. Once we have found the best parameters, the final models are tested on the test folds. We are aware that this means that our study has seen all the data at test time, although each fold's classifier has not. The reason why we took this approach was to compensate the small size of our dataset, so that we could have a considerable amount of samples tested.

When the number of samples per class is unbalanced as it is in our case (see Section 3.2), stratified cross-validation is used to maintain in each fold the general proportion of samples in each class in the whole dataset. This is something which has been shown to improve the bias and variance of the cross-validation (Kohavi, 1995).

However, as stated by Sechidis et al. (2011), this is more complicated in multi-label classification since the proportion of each class can be calculated in two ways. First, calculating the proportion of label sets (so unordered combinations of labels for each example) which in practical cases leads to have many label sets with only one instance. And second, calculating the general proportion by labels only, which is unsuitable to multi-label problems.

Instead of applying the aforementioned unsuitable procedures, very often practitioners use non-stratified random cross-validation. However, this entails that some rare classes might not have a single instance in one of the splits, which is problematic when calculating the metrics, and means the folds are not representative of the data in terms of number of samples per class.

Instead, Sechidis et al. (2011) proposed IterativeStratification. The algorithm first calculates the desired number of instances per k subset and the desired number of instances per label. Then iteratively checks every label with priority on those that have fewer instances (so that samples from rare labels are not wrongly distributed). Then for each example of that label, a subset is chosen based on the largest desired number of examples for the label, then the largest desired number of examples per subset, and finally ties are broken randomly.

3 Data and experimental setups

In this chapter we first explain how we created our dataset (Section 3.1) and perform an analysis of it (Section 3.2), and then introduce our experimental setup (Section 3.3) by looking at which implementations of the metrics we used, and how we carried out the experiments with the classifiers.

3.1 Dataset creation

The first step in creating our dataset was to crawl the websites listed in the Appendix in Chapter 5 to collect all HTML, PDF, DOCX documents from them with the Python library `Scrapy`. The most crucial website was the Knowledge Platform (UN, 2015), the main website of information for the SDGs. A collection of WPD (Word Perfect) documents was also collected but we decided to discard them since they had been created before 2015, when the SDGs were initiated.

Every document was also saved with their original URL or filename, since this would also be used later to extract the labels.

We then manually examined all the documents and discarded those that were created before 2015, as with the aforementioned WPD, or whose content was only about the Millennium Development Goals (MDG) (UN, 2000), the predecessors of the SDGs, which were created for the 2000-2015 period.

After that, we created a Python script to extract the SDGs texts from the documents. The script loops through all the documents and extracts plain text from them in multiple ways, depending the original format of the document.

To extract text from DOCX we used the package `python-docx` whereas for DOC we used `Antiword` through the Python module `subprocess`. If the latter failed to work, the script would then use MacOS' `textutil` to convert the document to TXT.

For PDF format we tried different packages such `PyPDF2` and `PDFMiner`. The latter, through the wrapper `slate3k` for Python 3 seemed to get better results and managed to extract texts with fewer corrupted characters. We had to adjust the `word_margin` parameter to avoid certain words being split. After the initial extraction we also needed to further split the paragraphs by `' . \n'` in order to get the actual paragraphs.

To parse HTML format, we used the `html.parser` from `Beautiful Soup`, then removed all the `script` and `style` tags with `decompose()` and finally looped through the stripped strings.

Additionally, when extracting every paragraph of each document, we checked if the language was English with `langdetect`, a port of `Google's Java language detection library`, since we found out that, even though during the crawling step we had filtered out by language, many texts were still in other languages. `Langdetect` works well to also eliminate some of the noisy data as it very often

fails to detect the language from very short texts or texts with very little actual text (and more numbers and other non-alpha symbols).

We then created a Text object with each paragraph from the documents, and stored it in a Document object. Every text object was processed with a series of filters such as removing leading and trailing spaces, numbered bullet points at the start of the string, reducing excessively repeated characters (for example —), new line symbols `\n`, vertical bars, and other noisy data.

We then looped through every paragraph of every document and separated those that contained SDGs labels from those that did not. We implemented two ways of extracting the labels. The first method consisted using regular expressions to search for a pattern in which the word *SDG* or *goal* appeared followed by a number in the filename of the document. If that was the case, we then saved that label in the document object and assumed that all texts included in that document were related to that label. For example, in the URL `www.sdgfund.org_goal-10-reduced-inequalities.html` we would assume that all texts extracted from that document belonged to goal 10.

This method also collected texts that are not related to that label. However, all labelled texts were later manually revised so we could eliminate those unrelated cases.

The second method also consisted in using regular expressions to look for combinations of keywords like *SDG*, *goal*, *target* or *indicator*, and a number in every paragraph of every document. Even though the targets and indicators include other reference numbers, they also contain the reference number of the goal, so we extracted labels from them using that information. For example, in the text (...) *includes a specific target (6.3) dedicated to water quality*, our script would find a match and extract the SDG label 6.

We also filtered out texts that contained the words *Millennium* and *MDG*, since even though we had filtered out Millennium Development Goals documents, there were still some texts with contained information about them. Additionally, any text that did not contain a label was stored in a unlabelled dataset that would also be used for training ULMFiT (see Section 3.3.4).

Every text was then collected together with their label and stored in a dictionary. If a new text had been previously added to the dictionary (i.e. if the same text was found in another document), we would then append the new labels to the old ones.

Additionally, we sped up the extraction by using Python Queues and Multiprocessing. Once the automatic extraction was done, both labelled and unlabelled datasets were finally saved in CSV format.

After that, the data was manually revised and cleaned. First the unlabelled data was cleaned using regular expressions. For example, many words containing dash, such as *gender-neutral* or *non-profit* had been separated during the extraction of the plain text. Similarly, many non-alphanumerical symbols would often appear in great proportion of certain samples. These issues, and many others, occurred from parsing some of the most difficult formats like PDF or DOC.

The unlabelled dataset is quite large (see Section 3.2), so there was only a limited amount of revision and cleaning that we could perform on it due to our limited time frame and resources. Even though some noise was still likely to be found in it, that did not pose a problem to our project since that data was

only used in one of our experiments — ULMFiT (see Section 3.3.4). In that experiment the unlabelled dataset was used to fine-tune a general model, and then the labelled data was used to train the classifier. For the rest of the experiments we only used the labelled data.

The labelled data was manually reviewed and cleaned in its totality. Since the segmentation of texts certain formats did not always work perfectly (especially with PDF), some texts included multiple paragraphs which had to be manually separated.

Some texts from the labelled dataset were also deleted since they were not correctly labelled, especially some of those obtained through the URL label lookup process. As mentioned before, not all the content in those documents was relevant to the label contained in the URL.

We also deleted the less informative texts, which were too short or did not contain any specific information about a specific label, like for example *Analysis and implementation of goal 8*.

Finally, another common issue found when manually checking the labelled dataset was our regular expressions matching text that was not an actual label. This happened most frequently because of text coming from bulleted text like titles or tables of content. For example, the text *1. Introducing the SDGs 2. How governments are(...)* originally is a table of content from a PDF document. Because PDF format can be very difficult to parse into plain text, in this case our script extracted the whole table of content as one text, instead of extracting line by line. Then the regular expression matches *SDGs 2* and therefore the whole text is incorrectly labelled with *SDG 2*.

3.2 Data analysis

In order to get some insights from our datasets, we run a data analysis on them. First, we calculated some raw metrics which can be seen in Table 3.1.

	Samples	Tokens	Vocabulary	L/S	S/L
Labelled	5,341	381,826	12,336	1.38	432.82
Unlabelled	248,303	17,826,903	232,946	N/A	N/A
Total	253,644	18,208,729	233,703	N/A	N/A

Table 3.1: Stats from two datasets. L/S represents the average number of labels per sample and S/L the average number of samples per label

These raw metrics were obtained using **Textacy**, a Python library built on top of the NLP library **Spacy** which helps create and get insights from corpora. The tokens and vocabulary numbers were obtained after tokenizing using the smallest Spacy **English language model**. As processing to obtain the size of the vocabulary we lowercased all words, and filtered out stop-words, punctuation and numbers. Finally, the total size of the vocabulary was calculated as the union of the labelled and unlabelled vocabulary sets.

In Figure 3.1 we see that the number of samples (texts) per class in the labelled dataset is quite unbalanced. While the average of samples per label is 432.82, the

Figure 3.1: Distribution of samples per class in the labelled dataset

class with the smallest number of samples (class 9, 271 samples) contains less than half samples than the class with the highest number (class 5, 637 samples).

Most of the samples (4449, 83.3% of the total) only have one label, as seen in Figure 3.2. Then 487 samples have two labels, 151 samples have three labels, and so on until the number gets very small. This gives us an average of 1.38 labels per sample, as seen in Table 3.1. This is likely to be a positive aspect of our labelled dataset as it might be simpler to learn features from samples that only have one label, than those that have multiple.

In Figure 3.3 we can also see that most samples (4105, 76.86% of the total) contain between 1 and 100 tokens, followed by 874 samples (16.36% of the total) which contain between 101 and 200 tokens, which is an important aspect to bear in mind when running some of the deep learning experiments where there is a length limitation.

As mentioned in Section 3.1, one of the methods we used to label the samples was to extract the label from the texts with regular expressions. If we look at how many of the samples contain an explicit mention of the SDGs labels, we see that there are a total of 2843 (53.23% of the total) of such samples, which represent approximately half of our labelled dataset.

This is relevant for our experiments since our classifiers can learn to classify texts by identifying these labels in the samples, as explained in Section 3.3.5.

In Figure 3.4, we can see a label co-occurrence heat map, which represents all those labels that co-occur in the samples, with the darker shades showing those labels with more co-occurrences. As we can see, the labels with most co-occurrences are 1-2, 1-3, 1-5, 1-8, and 2-3. It is not surprising that zero hunger, no poverty and good health are all very closely related.

Figure 3.2: Distribution of number of labels per sample in the labelled dataset

Figure 3.3: Number of tokens per sample in the labelled dataset. Token numbers are intervals, so the first is between 0 and 100 tokens, the second between 101 and 200, and so on.

Figure 3.4: Label co-occurrence heat map from the labelled dataset

3.3 Experimental setups

In this section we discuss the different system implementations and experimental setups of our project.

In our experiments we explored multi-label text classification since each sample or text of our labelled dataset can be assigned one or more of the 17 SDG classes. Furthermore, we considered that it would be interesting to have a baseline with the machine learning methods explained in Section 2.3 and see how they would compare against the deep learning methods with transfer learning from Section 2.4. With these experiments we also wanted to see what impact a small dataset like ours can have on each method, with the hypothesis that machine learning approaches tend to obtain better results than neural networks when the dataset is small, something which transfer learning is to tackle, as we explained in Section 2.5.

Regarding our technical setup, all the experiments except for those with BERT were carried out in [Jupyter](#) notebooks, using [Google Colaboratory](#) with one NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU and 12GB of RAM. The experiments with BERT were considerably computationally expensive and therefore we used [Google Cloud Platform](#) with four NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPUs and 64GB of RAM for those.

3.3.1 Evaluation and cross-validation

The classifiers were evaluated with the implementation from [Scikit Learn](#) (Pedregosa et al., 2011) of the metrics explained in Section 2.6.

For the multi-label stratified cross-validation explained in Section 2.6.4 we used a publicly available¹ implementation done by Trent J. Bradberry.

All experiments were carried out with a 5-fold cross-validation, instead of the more common 10-fold since some of the classifiers were very computationally expensive. We therefore first saved the indices of the samples for each fold with a split of 80% training, 10% validation and 10% test, with around 4270 samples for training, 520 for validation and 540 for test for each fold. The stratification was done between the training set and the test set. From the training set we separated 10% of the data using a shuffle split for the test folds.

For each experiment we used exactly the same fold indices. We then trained each classifier on each fold, and fine-tuned the hyper-parameters with the validation set. Once we found the best hyper-parameters, we used the trained classifier to predict the labels from the test set. The results were obtained from each fold and averaged over 5.

3.3.2 Machine learning

The baseline experiments with the multinomial Naive Bayes, SVM, logistic regression and kNN algorithms were carried out using [Scikit Learn's](#) (Pedregosa et al., 2011) implementations: `MultinomialNB`, `LinearSVC`, `LogisticRegression` and `KNeighborsClassifier`, respectively.

As a first step in our experiments with the machine learning methods, we found the best parameters for each algorithm through `GridSearchCV` with a `Pipeline` with the training and validation data. `GridSearchCV` runs exhaustively a classifier with different parameters we choose while performing cross-validation with the folds provided by us, and then returns the best parameters and the scores achieved.

The `Pipeline`, on the other hand, helped us combine transforms that we do to the data with our classifier.

We chose an OVR transform approach for the classifiers, which means that a classifier is created for each class. In order to do that we binarized our labels. For example, if a sample had labels 1 and 4, they would get binarized to $1_1, 0_2, 0_3, 1_4, 0_5, \dots, 0_{17}$ where the subscript number corresponds to the class.

As a second and final step of our experiments, we trained the model again after pre-processing the data and test the classifiers with the test data folds.

The pre-processing aforementioned consisted of striping spaces, filtering out punctuation and stop words, tokenizing, and returning the lemmas from the nouns, verbs, adverbs and adjectives. To do this, we used [NLTK's](#) tokenizer, lemmatizer, and stop words.

After pre-processing, we vectorized the texts with TF-IDF and run the training with the best parameters found in the previous step.

3.3.3 Word embeddings

We run our experiments with pre-trained word embeddings with [Keras](#) (Chollet et al., 2015) with some variations from model to model which are pointed out in the next sections. We use CNNs for all the experiments since, as mentioned in Section 2.4.1 they can obtain comparable results to RNNs, and are much faster to

¹ github.com/trent-b/iterative-stratification

run. Since we train multiple computationally expensive models, we decided this would be a good option for these experiments.

Word2vec

We first tokenized the data with NLTK's tokenizer, and then loaded the pre-trained Word2vec embeddings using [gensim](#) (Řehůřek and Sojka, 2010) with a dimensionality of 300 and a window of 5.

We limited our vocabulary to the 20000 most frequent words from our samples. We then created an embedding layer by converting the texts to Word2vec embeddings. When a word did not have an embedding representation, it was set as zero in the layer.

This embedding layer was then fit to a convolutional 1D layer with a Xavier uniform initializer, with average and max pooling which is then passed to a dense layer with a sigmoid activation. We finally compiled our model with a binary cross-entropy loss function and the RMSprop optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001. The classifier was run 10 epochs for each cross-validation fold with a batch size of 16 and a maximum length sequence of 512.

GloVe

For the GloVe experiments, we tokenized the data with Keras tokenizer. For the embeddings, we first downloaded them from the Stanford NLP group website² and then loaded them directly from the TXT file, `glove.6B.300d.txt`, with 300 dimensions.

The architecture of the classifier was otherwise the same as that of Word2vec.

ELMo

For ELMo's experiments, we loaded the word embeddings using [TensorFlow's Hub](#), a TensorFlow library of pre-trained models.

We then tokenized the data with the [Moses tokenizer](#), the same used by the ELMo authors when creating the embeddings. We passed the embeddings layer to two dense layers, one with a rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation and the last one with a sigmoid activation, and finally trained 6 epochs with a binary cross-entropy loss function and RMSprop with the default learning rate of 0.001. The maximum sequence length was in this case set to 128 tokens, since ELMo was really computationally expensive to run.

3.3.4 Fine-tuning language models

ULMFiT

For the ULMFiT experiments we used its original environment, Howard et al. (2018)'s Fastai, a high-level library built on top of [PyTorch](#) that simplifies experimentation with neural networks. Additionally, we used Fastai's implementation of the LSTM architecture from Merity et al. (2017).

²nlp.stanford.edu/projects/glove/

Based on Howard and Ruder (2018), we did not train our model from scratch, but instead used a pretrained language model on Merity et al. (2016)'s [WikiText-103](#). The idea is comprised of two steps. We first trained the last layers of the pretrained WikiText-103 language model with our unlabelled data. In this step the next word is used as the label for every word, with the idea that the model will learn knowledge from the SDGs. Then a text classifier is trained on top of that language model with the labelled data.

In the first step, and using the ideas from Howard and Ruder (2018) on *discriminative fine-tuning, and gradual unfreezing*, we trained the model one epoch, then unfroze the model and trained again for 10 epochs. In this part we used 80% of our unlabelled data (198642 samples) for training and the rest (49661 samples) for validation. The model finally achieved an accuracy of 0.44, which means that it is capable of predicting almost half of the words correctly. Then we save the encoder of the language model.

Fastai offers the possibility of checking the output of the model with the `predict()` method. This method accepts the start of a sentence such as *African countries like (...)* as a parameter, and the length of the desired output. When run, the method will output the rest of the sentence as predicted by the model. For example, one of the predictions that we obtained was *African countries like Benin and Burkina Faso face particularly serious obstacles to economic development , which require , among others (...)*. This shows us that our language model contains some knowledge of the world.

In the second step, we trained a text classifier on top of the language model's encoder that we trained in the previous step. More specifically, we fine-tuned our pre-trained model. Here again, we used Howard and Ruder (2018)'s ideas of *discriminative fine-tuning, slanted triangular learning rates, and gradual unfreezing*.

We first unfroze the last two layers of the network and trained one epoch. Unfreezing here means that we only fit the last n layers of the model (discriminative fine-tuning). We did this step once again (gradual unfreezing) but unfroze the last three layers instead. In this epoch and the ones from the next step, we use slanted triangular learning rates, which means that the learning rate is lower in the first layer and it increases in the subsequent layers until the last one. The intuition behind this is that we want the model to learn more in the last layers which are closely related to our labelled data, not the general model. Finally, we trained the whole model (all of its layers) ten epochs.

An important advantage of this method is that whereas training the language model is time-consuming (in our case it took around 5 hours), we only need to do it once and then we can save the model. After that, we can simply load it and run different experiments on the text classifier, whose training set is much smaller, and try different parameters and changes since every epoch takes up to one and a half minutes per epoch in the environment we were using.

BERT

For our experiments with BERT we used [FastBert](#), a Fastai-inspired library that helps carrying out deep learning experiments using BERT pre-trained models and relies on [PyTorch-Transformers](#) (Wolf et al., 2019), a Pytorch port of BERT.

FastBert uses `PyTorch-Transformers'` `BertForSequenceClassification`, which is a BERT model transformer with a sequence classification head on top, which is a linear layer on top of the pooled output from the transformer.

We used the uncased large BERT model, which has 24 layers, 1024 hidden layers, 340 million parameters and was trained on lowercased English text. Contrary to ULMFiT, we did not use our unlabelled data to fine-tune the model, but directly fine-tuned the model with our labelled data for 3 epochs only for each cross-validation fold with a learning rate of 0.001 and a maximum sequence length of 512.

Additionally, we used a warmup linear optimizer schedule with 500 warmup steps. This means that the learning rate linearly increases from 0 to 1 over a warmup number of training steps (500, in our case), and then decreases in the rest of the training steps. We also used half-precision floating-point format (FP16), which uses less memory and allow us to train faster without hindering the results.

3.3.5 Masking experiments

As mentioned in Section 3.2, 53.23% of all the labelled samples contain their labels explicitly in the text. This means that our classifiers might perform well if they learn to identify these labels, which would be the same as back-engineering the process we used to create the dataset. In a real case scenario, most of the samples would not have explicit labels, as it is shown by the size of our unlabelled dataset, so we want our classifiers to learn other features that are not these explicit labels.

Therefore, we carried out all our experiments in two ways, with the untouched original dataset and with masked labels. Masking the labels means that all these explicit mentions of the labels in the text were substituted by the keyword `SDGLABEL` before feeding the texts to the classifiers for training. For example, *Goal 8: Decent work (...)* becomes `SDGLABEL: Decent work (...)`. This masking was performed in the training and validation data only and not in the test set with the idea that the test set should be as representative as possible of a real case scenario, so we left those test samples completely untouched.

These masking experiments can give us an idea of not only the impact that taking out these labels can have on the results but also which classifiers are best at learning other features which are not the explicit labels.

4 Results and discussion

In this section we evaluate the results of our experiments on the test set qualitatively and quantitatively.

4.1 Quantitative analysis

In Table 4.1 we can see the results on micro averaged precision, recall and F1 score, as well as AUROC, for both the masked and non-masked experiments.

	Non-masked				Masked			
	P_{mic}	R_{mic}	$F1_{mic}$	AUC	P_{mic}	R_{mic}	$F1_{mic}$	AUC
NB	0.87	0.64	0.74	0.82	0.86	0.57	0.69	0.78
KNN	0.88	0.62	0.73	0.81	0.87	0.55	0.67	0.77
LG	0.82	0.80	0.81	0.89	0.74	0.71	0.73	0.84
SVM	0.89	0.77	0.82	0.88	0.83	0.66	0.74	0.82
W2V	0.61	0.55	0.58	0.76	0.58	0.45	0.50	0.71
GloVe	0.75	0.70	0.72	0.84	0.72	0.65	0.68	0.81
ELMo	0.64	0.65	0.64	0.81	0.64	0.61	0.62	0.79
ULMFiT	0.76	0.78	0.77	0.88	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.86
BERT	0.82	0.85	0.84	0.92	0.80	0.83	0.81	0.91

Table 4.1: Micro-averaged precision, recall and F1, and AUROC for every classifier on the test set.

For better visual reference, the precision and recall for both masked and non-masked experiments have been plotted in Figure 4.1.

In general, we observe that the drop from the non-masked to the masked results in terms of F1 scores is higher in all the machine learning models and in Word2Vec than in the rest of the models. More specifically, there is a 5% drop in NB, 6% in kNN, 8% in LG, 8% in SVM and 8% in Word2Vec, compared to 2% in ELMo, 3% ULMFiT, and 3% in BERT. This could be due to the fact that pre-trained language representations (with the exception of Word2Vec in this case) incorporate world knowledge to the classifier and therefore help finding underlying information that otherwise would be very difficult to find by relying on the information contained in the samples only.

It is also interesting that almost all the models tend to have more precision than recall except for ELMo, ULMFiT and BERT on the non-masked experiments and ULMFiT and BERT in both the masked and non-masked experiments.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that BERT is not only the most effective model with micro-averaged F1 scores of 0.81 and 0.84 in masked and non-masked

experiments, respectively, but it also presents the best scores in AUROC with 0.91 and 0.92 in the masked and non-masked experiments.

In NB, KNN and SVM, the differences between precision and recall are considerable, especially with the kNN classifier. However, as we move on to the pre-trained language representation models, the differences seem to start decreasing perhaps, as we mentioned before, due to the fact that these models contain more world-knowledge and the classification is not based on the content of the samples only. As an exception, LG presents also a small difference between precision and recall.

It is also noteworthy that models like LG and SVM achieve almost as good F1 scores as BERT in both the non-masked and masked experiments, with the only exception of ULMFiT in the masked experiments, which achieved the same F1 score as the LG model. These results might be linked to the small size of our labelled dataset, which has been shown to generally affect neural networks in a negative way.

However, whereas SVM achieved the second best results in terms of F1 scores in the non-masked experiments, LG and ULMFiT present higher and equal AUROC scores, with 0.89 and 0.88 respectively, compared to 0.88 from the SVM.

On the masked experiments, the second best AUROC scores (0.86) are achieved by ULMFiT, even though it has the same F1 score as the SVM, 0.74, which also shows that the knowledge provided by the pre-trained language model from ULMFiT might be helping in the classification task.

Nevertheless, we had the expectation that ELMo and ULMFiT would obtain higher F1 scores than the ones achieved — 0.64 and 0.77 for the non-masked experiments respectively, and than 0.62 and 0.74 for the masked experiments.

Figure 4.1: Micro-averaged precision and recall of non-masked and masked experiments from all the classifiers on the test set.

In Table 4.2 we can see the F1 scores of the models per class. Looking at the results of our best model, BERT, we observe the highest scores are obtained with class 4 (0.87), quality education; class 6 (0.87), clean water and sanitation; class 14 (0.92), life below water; and class 16 (0.87), sustainable cities and communities. On the other hand, the worst results, both with a F1 score of 0.70, come from classes 1, no poverty; and 10, reduced inequalities.

These results might be also due to the specificity of the content of these SDGs. The aforementioned group of higher F1 scores seem to be more specific than SDGs 1 and 10, which can be seen as somehow more general. These classes also overlap with other classes more frequently than the others (see the label co-occurrence heat map in Figure 3.4 from Section 3.2), which could explain why it might be more difficult to classify them.

C	NB	KNN	LG	SVM	W2V	GLoVe	ELMo	ULMFiT	BERT
1	0.51	0.49	0.57	0.57	0.48	0.50	0.40	0.58	0.70
2	0.64	0.56	0.74	0.73	0.36	0.66	0.62	0.62	0.83
3	0.70	0.72	0.74	0.74	0.48	0.71	0.70	0.72	0.82
4	0.65	0.66	0.76	0.73	0.61	0.74	0.71	0.69	0.87
5	0.73	0.70	0.79	0.80	0.75	0.74	0.77	0.71	0.83
6	0.68	0.67	0.76	0.76	0.62	0.71	0.65	0.89	0.87
7	0.71	0.67	0.78	0.76	0.69	0.73	0.66	0.76	0.86
8	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.69	0.45	0.62	0.57	0.80	0.74
9	0.59	0.63	0.67	0.64	0.23	0.58	0.40	0.70	0.76
10	0.62	0.54	0.64	0.64	0.24	0.53	0.50	0.73	0.70
11	0.72	0.71	0.77	0.79	0.34	0.71	0.66	0.77	0.86
12	0.64	0.67	0.70	0.72	0.47	0.63	0.56	0.79	0.77
13	0.55	0.56	0.60	0.63	0.53	0.55	0.50	0.78	0.75
14	0.85	0.80	0.86	0.86	0.62	0.83	0.81	0.79	0.92
15	0.71	0.68	0.75	0.74	0.51	0.71	0.60	0.78	0.83
16	0.72	0.71	0.75	0.78	0.39	0.73	0.66	0.64	0.87
17	0.69	0.69	0.65	0.71	0.40	0.60	0.50	0.68	0.73

Table 4.2: Micro-averaged F1 scores per class from the masked experiments on the test set. C stands for class.

However, these results might be also related to the number of samples per class. In Table 4.2 we can see the the relation between the amount of samples and the F1 scores per class for both the masked and unmasked experiments. The F1 scores are calculated by adding all the F1 scores per labels and normalized over the number of experiments (9). The number of samples were obtained by calculating the number of samples per label (so the percentage of samples per label with respect the total number of samples) over the total multiplied by 10.

This size-scores co-relation can be particularly seen in classes 9, 10 and 13, which are the classes with the lowest number of samples (see also Section 3.2) and with the lowest F1 scores in both the masked and non-masked experiments.

It is also noteworthy that the scores for class 17 go down even though it has a higher number of samples than most classes. This might be due, again, to the

fact that the content of this class is more difficult to identify, since the topic is less explicit.

Figure 4.2: Normalized stacked micro-averaged F1 scores of all the classifiers for each class (in masked and non-masked experiments) compared to the normalized distribution of samples multiplied by ten.

We also compared the effectiveness of our BERT classifier on the masked experiments by the three dimensions proposed by Rockström and Sukhdev (2016) — society, environment and economy. Please notice that we changed *biosphere* to *environment*. The results can be seen in Table 4.3.

The environment group obtains better results even though it does not have a higher average number of samples, compared to the society group. The reason for this might be, again as mentioned before, the more specific content of this group, whereas the society and economy groups involve somehow more general and broader information.

Class	Samples	Prec	Rec	F1
Society				
1	394	0.73	0.70	0.70
2	452	0.79	0.88	0.83
3	570	0.81	0.83	0.82
4	360	0.89	0.84	0.87
5	637	0.78	0.88	0.83
7	438	0.86	0.86	0.86
11	411	0.83	0.91	0.86
16	477	0.86	0.89	0.87
Avg.	467.375	0.82	0.85	0.83
Environment				
6	396	0.85	0.91	0.87
13	306	0.76	0.74	0.75
14	625	0.94	0.90	0.92
15	392	0.81	0.86	0.83
Avg.	429.75	0.84	0.85	0.84
Economy				
8	387	0.72	0.76	0.74
9	271	0.73	0.79	0.76
10	309	0.70	0.70	0.70
12	361	0.78	0.78	0.77
17	572	0.70	0.75	0.73
Avg.	380	0.73	0.76	0.74

Table 4.3: Micro-averaged precision, recall and F1 scores of BERT per class grouped in three dimensions. These results are from the masked experiments.

4.2 Qualitative Analysis

As addition to the quantitative overview from above, in this section we analyze some common errors and insights we discovered when looking at the results per sample from the test set.

To carry out this analysis we collected the predicted labels for all the test samples from each of the 5 folds from the cross-validation. For that reason, some texts appeared more than once in our results, and they sometimes presented different predictions for each fold since every fold has a slightly different training set. Whenever we found such cases, we kept the most representative predictions (those that repeated the most) for that sample.

All the predictions from our classifiers mentioned in the next sections belong to the masked experiments, except when otherwise explicitly mentioned.

4.2.1 Samples with many labels

All the classifiers, both in the masked and non-masked experiments, made the most errors, and therefore had the highest Hamming loss (HL) scores, in those samples that had more than one label assigned. One reason to explain this might

be that these texts tend to be longer and more complex, which makes them more difficult to classify. Additionally, texts with multiple labels also contain multiple cues and components which refer to different classes, and therefore distinguishing them becomes harder than when we only have one class.

Many of these texts with multiple labels also tend to contain less information about the SDGs themselves. For example, the sample *Strengthening the protection and sustainable management of natural capital as a base for social prosperity and transition to a low-carbon economy (linked to SDGs 6, 7, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15)*, explains that these SDGs are linked to the management of natural capital. However, when these labels are masked, there is not much more information in the text itself which can hint the classifier why this sample should be classified with those labels specifically. In the example above, all the classifiers failed to find the right label in the masked experiments with some exceptions. NB, kNN and LG managed to find the last label, 15, and BERT found 1, 3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 15, with a HL of 0.29. This could also indicate that BERT is better than the other models to find those underlying connections of the SDGs.

In some instances, the transfer learning models seem to be considerably effective at finding the correct labels even in long and complex texts. For example, in the text below (which has been shortened from its original length), BERT was able to find all four labels, 1, 5, 8, 10, and ELMo was able to find three of them — 5, 8, 10.

(...) household asset surveys for Ecuador and Ghana, the authors find that 24 per cent of all households with migrants in Ecuador and 17 per cent in Ghana have acquired at least one asset through the use of remittances (...). In Ecuador, where international migration is gender balanced, male and female international migrants are equally likely to send remittances to their households of origin; (...) In Ghana, most businesses acquired with remittances are owned by women (...). In Ecuador, women managers have benefited through the build-up of their savings and as joint owners of the homes built with remittances; (...) Enhancing the capacity of migrants to channel their foreign savings towards asset accumulation will require policy interventions at various levels, including a focus on their conditions of employment in destination countries (...)

4.2.2 Samples without any contextual information

In some cases, samples that lack any contextual information are present in our dataset. For example, the sample *Table 3: Targets and indicators for SDG 11 Target description Core indicator Tier* has very limited information to identify the label, apart from the label itself. In these cases, if the label is masked, the classifiers are unable to correctly classify the sample. In the example above, for instance, none of the classifiers managed to return label 11. On the other hand, on the non-masked experiments, NB, LG, SVM and GloVe managed to identify the label, 11, from the text.

4.2.3 Non-numerical explicit label information

Apart from their number, the labels can also be textually identified by their official name. For example, in the text *The EU made strongest progress over the last 5 years*

towards the overall achievement of SDG 3 'good health and well-being', followed by SDG 4 'quality education' and SDG 7 'affordable and clean energy' the labels are not only mentioned by their number, but also by their name.

This information, the naming of the SDGs and their targets and indicators, is repeated throughout our dataset in considerable number, which should help our classifiers identify the labels. However, it seems like ULMFiT and BERT are the models that better handle the classification of these samples. In the above example, they were able to return labels 3, 4 and 7, whereas other models like SVM or GloVe were able to return only two of those labels.

4.2.4 Limitations of the initial labelling

Sometimes the models classified some samples into classes that the samples could actually belong to but were not included in our dataset in the first place. For example, *6km women in Africa walk 6km (on average) to collect water* was initially labelled with label 6 (clean water and sanitation), when we created our dataset. However, ELMo assigned the text with label 5 (gender equality), and BERT classified it with labels 6 and 5. In this case, even though this sample is labelled in our dataset as label 6, it could have also been classified with label 5.

It was also interesting to see how sometimes certain models (like the machine learning ones) obtain better results than the larger, more modern ones in simple texts with few labels. For example, *The "Good Garden" in Serbia not only a social enterprise for growing organic vegetables but also a training centre for for women survivors of domestic violence who wish to get involved in this sustainable farming method.* had initially labels 5 (gender equality), and 12 (responsible consumption). In this sample, BERT assigned it the labels 2 (zero hunger) and 5 instead, while it was 100% correctly labelled with 5 and 12 by NB, LG, Word2Vec and GloVe.

Of course, this sample could also be related to zero hunger since they mention growing organic vegetables, which shows how difficult it can be sometimes to differentiate between the classes.

5 Conclusions and prospects for future work

We have tested different multi-label text classification approaches for SDGs documents in order to help users find related information in a more efficient way. In order to carry out these experiments, we built a corpus comprising labelled and unlabelled texts from crawled SDGs-related documents from the web.

We conclude that the fine-tuning pre-trained language model BERT obtains the best results in terms of F1 score and AUROC. However, it was also interesting that much less computationally expensive methods like SVM and LG were almost as effective as BERT in terms of F1 measure. We believe this might be due to the small size of the labelled data.

In terms of qualitative results, we see it is quite challenging for all the models to classify texts with multiple labels, although the fine-tuning pre-trained models (ULMFiT and BERT) seem to be able to handle these better.

We also found out that the models sometimes classified certain samples with labels that the dataset did not contain for those samples initially, but that were correct. This brings up the issue of how complex it is to draw the limit between such interconnected labels like the SDGs. We are aware that our approach when creating the dataset is somehow naive as we assumed that texts that explicitly mention a certain SDG would only be about those SDGs. In reality, however, this does not always hold.

In terms of future work we see many areas of improvement and expansion. One idea would be increasing the size of the dataset by using the best classifier, the one trained with BERT, to label samples from the unlabelled dataset (or from newly crawled documents) and manually check them afterwards. It would be interesting to see how much the results might improve by, for instance, doubling the size of the labelled dataset. Additionally, it would be also interesting to see if the SVM would still have close results to those from BERT.

Another part of our project that could benefit from further improvement is the extraction of plain text from file types like PDF or DOC which are quite challenging to parse. We found that many samples needed to be removed from our initial labelled dataset during the manual checking process due to bad formatting issues, which makes the process very time-consuming.

Another area worth exploring would be the extraction of labels not only from the goals, but also from the targets and indicators. This would mean finding more specific and fine-grained information. In fact, we carried out a few tests doing this at the start of the thesis. We extracted not only SDGs labels, but targets and indicators as well. However, the data was insufficient and many of the targets and indicators did not have a single sample that represented them. So in order to do this more data would need to be gathered first.

It would be also interesting to look at some approaches on how to deal with label imbalance, such as over-sampling (B. Liu and Tsoumakas, 2019) or ensemble methods (Galar et al., 2012), and see how these would affect the current results.

Finally, another interesting area to expand this project can be trying other fine-tuning pre-trained models that we did not explore in this thesis, such as GPT-2, XLM or any of those mentioned in Section 2.5.2.

Appendix

URLs of websites crawled for the creation of our dataset.

sustainabledevelopment.un.org
sdgfund.org
undp.org/content/undp/en/home/sustainable-development-goals
un.org/sustainabledevelopment
globalgoals.org
unwomen.org/en/news/in-focus/women-and-the-sdgs
en.unesco.org/sdgs
who.int/sdg/en
fao.org/sustainable-development-goals/en
sdgfund.org
government.se/government-policy/the-global-goals-and-the-2030-Agenda-for-sustainable-development
unglobalcompact.org/what-is-gc/our-work/sustainable-development
unglobalcompact.org/sdgs
ec.europa.eu/europeaid/policies/sustainable-development-goals_en
unenvironment.org/explore-topics/sustainable-development-goals
worldslargestlessonindia.globalgoals.org

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